

DISPERSOID INOCULANTS INFLUENCE ON THE WELD METAL SECONDARY MICROSTRUCTURE FORMATION

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Abstract

The influence of dispersed inoculants (phase inclusions) in the form of refractory compounds TiC, SiC and ZrO₂ on the kinetics of structural transformations in the high-strength low-alloy steels weld metal has been investigated. The various types inoculants effect on the bainitic transformation shift to the higher temperatures region is shown. Using transmission electron microscopy, the structural-phase changes nature in the formation of the bainite structure is analyzed: the fragmentation features, the dislocation density distribution and the carbide phase precipitation morphology.

Keywords: Inoculation process; mechanical properties; microstructures; precipitation hardening; grain boundary dislocation density distribution; carbide phase precipitation morphology.

Introduction

The current state of steel production analysis in the world shows a stable growth tendency, both in the total volume of smelting and a constant increase in the level of requirements for metal quality [1]. At the same time, the share of high-strength low-alloy steels in the ferrous metallurgy range increases markedly [2]. It is noted that in order to achieve higher values strength, ductility and crack resistance of steels used in various technology fields, it is necessary to develop new non-traditional approaches to the formation of the structure of such materials [3]. The possibility of influencing on most optimal structural components nucleation and growth by introducing (inoculating) refractory nonmetallic inclusions into the metal melt is considered as one of the promising directions in solving this problem [4, 5]. At the same time, it was found that the non-metallic inclusions role, which, as a rule, negatively affecting on steels mechanical properties complex, changes under certain conditions: with a decrease in their size, the negative effect of inclusions decreases [6, 7], and finely dispersed inclusions with a certain composition and morphology can be used to control structural components nucleation and growth processes. Such inclusions are called "dispersoids" [8, 9].

For example, dispersed inoculants are used in the smelting of high-strength low-alloy steels in order to form the required structural composition [10-12]. There are a number studies showing the prospects of introducing inoculants into the weld pool [13]. This work is also devoted to the study the effect of dispersoid inoculants on the conditions for weld metal of high-strength low-alloy steels structure and the mechanical properties formation.

The studies were carried out on weld metals samples obtained by welding with flux-cored wire in a shielding gas (Ar + CO₂) low-alloy high-strength steel butt joints in accordance with the requirements of ISO 26304. The investigated weld metals chemical composition is given in Table 1.

When choosing the composition of dispersed inoculants, we proceeded from the fact that, in accordance with published data [14-16], the structural components formation depends both on the free energy value

of their nucleation at the a metallic matrix interface with non-metallic inclusions, and on the physico-chemical characteristics of inclusions and transformations temperature range.

Experimental Procedure

It was shown in [17] that the introduction of refractory inclusions TiC, SiC, ZrO₂ in the dispersed inoculants form into the weld pool affects the grains morphology of the primary structure formed during of the weld metal crystallization. We have an interest to investigate the relationship between the inoculants effect on the primary metal structure and the welds secondary microstructure formation. The above refractory compounds in the dispersed particles form were inoculated into the weld pool by introducing them into a flux-cored wire core. The results obtained were compared with the data obtained during weld metal welding with similar technological process parameters, but without the use of dispersed inoculants (weld metal symbol 0). For a clearer identification of the inoculation effect, the data obtained when testing the weld metal samples TiC, SiC and ZrO₂ were compared with the results of studying the weld metal alloyed with titanium (weld metal symbol Ti) without the inoculants introduction.

Weld metals structural analysis was carried out using a light microscope "NEOPHOT-30" at magnifications from x200 to x1000. The digital image was recorded using an Olympus digital camera. The microhardness of the structural components was measured on a LECO M-400 hardness tester at loads of 100 g (HV0.1) and 1 kg (HV10), respectively, according to GOST 2999. To identify the features of the microstructure, a JSM-840 scanning electron microscope (JEOL) was used, equipped with a MicroCapture image capture system with its subsequent registration on the monitor screen, and a JSM 35 scanning electron microscope equipped with a Link energy dispersive analyzer.

The samples microstructure was revealed by the chemical etching method in a 4% alcoholic solution of nitric acid. Samples for research were prepared according to standard methods using various dispersion diamond pastes. The size of the structural components was determined in accordance with GOST 5639.

A fine structure direct study was carried out with a transmission microscope JEM-200 CX setup (JEOL) at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV in order to study the weld metal fine (dislocation) structure, substructure, as well as details of grain boundaries and subboundaries. Foils for electron microscopic studies were prepared by the electroerosive cutting methods with subsequent mechanical thinning on sanding papers with different grain sizes, preliminary electrolytic thinning of prepared washers ($d = 3\text{mm}$) followed by final ion thinning.

The structural transformations nature in the weld metal was studied by simulating the thermal deformation cycle of welding using a Gleeble 3800 complex equipped with a high-speed dilatometer. The studies

were carried out using cylindrical specimens with a 6.0 mm diameter and a 80 mm length, made in weld metal across the weld center line.

Experimental results and discussion

The dilatometric studies results showed that the inoculants introduction promotes an increase in the austenite decomposition temperature upon cooling the weld metal (Ac_3), as well as the start (B_s) and finish (B_f) of the bainite transformation (Table 1), while alloying with titanium gives the opposite effect. Such changes in the critical points position of structural transformations affected both the primary structure grain size (d_γ in Table 1) and weld metal the secondary structure composition (Table 2).

Table 1

Austenite grain size and critical points of structural transformations in weld metals

Weld metal	d_γ , μm	Ac_3 , $^\circ\text{C}$	B_s , $^\circ\text{C}$	B_f , $^\circ\text{C}$
0	70 ± 5	843	603	430
Ti	45 ± 5	840	583	432
SiC	80 ± 6	851	644	435
ZrO ₂	90 ± 7	859	662	461
TiC	80 ± 6	870	648	435

Optical microscopy data showed that the weld metal secondary microstructure consists a bainite-martensite mixture with an insignificant amount of a ferrite component (Fig. 1). Bainite is represented by morphological forms of upper, lower and intragranular bainite,

ferrite with broken polygonal segregations and Widmanstedt ferrite along grain boundaries. Martensite is formed in the a traditional acircular structure form.

The weld metals secondary structure composition

<p>20μm Электронное изображение 1</p>	
<p>20μm Электронное изображение 1</p>	
<p>20μm Электронное изображение 1</p>	
<p>20μm Электронное изображение 1</p>	
<p>20μm Электронное изображение 1</p>	
<p><i>Fig. 1 Weld metal microstructure (Neophot 30) Images received by PhD Ermolenko D.Yu.</i></p>	<p><i>Fig. 2 Weld metal microstructure (JSM-840) Images received by PhD Stepanuk S.M. Images received by PhD Stepanuk S.M.</i></p>

*Fig. 1 Weld metal microstructure (Neophot 30)
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As can be seen from the data presented, alloying the weld metal with titanium (Ti weld), as well as inoculating TiC and SiC, contributed to an increase in the proportion of upper bainite in the microstructure and a decrease in the content of the ferrite component, while the introduction of ZrO₂ dispersoids into the weld pool had the opposite effect.

The results of weld metal mechanical properties determining, given in Table 3, showed that, despite the

absence of changes in the martensite content, the bainite phase content in the structural components of the weld metal 0 and ZrO₂, as well as Ti, SiC and TiC, is similar in composition. mechanical properties differ (strength, ductility and toughness). In addition, attention is drawn to the noticeable difference in the level of the weld metal ZrO₂ structural components composition and mechanical properties.

Table 3

Mechanical properties of weld metals							
Weld metal	σ_B ,	$\sigma_{0.2}$,	δ ,	ψ ,	Sk,	KCV, J/cm ²	
	MPa	MPa	%	%	MPa	+ 20 °C	- 20 °C
0	775	738	16	54	1384	61	43
Ti	746	689	19	60	1865	60	57
SiC	726	650	21	62	1910	85	65
ZrO ₂	645	556	21	60	1612	116	98
TiC	728	665	19	61	1867	82	63

σ_B - tensile strength at room temperature,

$\sigma_{0.2}$ - yield strength at room temperature,

δ - relative elongation,

ψ - relative reduction

Sk - true stress at room temperature,

KCV - impact strength

For a more detailed dispersoids inoculation effect analysis in the weld pool on the weld metal structure formation processes, the transmission electron microscopy methods were used. Figure 3 shows typical images of the investigated welds metal structural components, the fragmentation features, phase precipitates in them, and the dislocation density distribution.

Analysis of the structural contribution and phase parameters to the change in the weld metals strength characteristics, carried out with the developed experimental and analytical approach to assessing the structure parameters differentiated contribution to the weld metal mechanical characteristics [18], showed that in

all considered weld metal samples the greatest contribution to strengthening introduces a lath substructure and dispersed particles of phase precipitates. A sharp increase in hardening, characteristic of upper bainite, characterized by a dislocations high density [$\rho \sim (2...3) \cdot 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$] along the boundaries of the lath structure and the most saturated phase precipitates in this area, leads to an increase in dislocation and dispersion hardening.

As can be seen from the above study results, the dispersed inoculants introduction into the weld pool is accompanied by a change in the carbide phase morphology, which should help stabilize the structure and improve the properties of the weld metal [19].

Fig. 3. Structure formation features of the upper and lower bainite, the dislocations density distribution, the carbide phase precipitation and its diffraction pattern in the various types welds metal: a - "0"; b - ZrO₂; c - SiC; d - TiC.

Images received by PhD Kushnareva O.S.

The presence of refractory dispersoids in the solidifying weld metal causes a partial cementite precipitates replacement at grain boundaries with alloyed type carbides Me_7C_3 , $Me_{23}C_6$, and Me_3C_2 , which makes it possible to reduce the inhomogeneity of the dislocation density distribution at the grain boundaries. In cases

where an increase in substructural hardening is provided by a fine-grained fragmented substructure formation, with a uniform the dislocation density distribution, the phase precipitates particles have a uniform distribution, there are no areas in the form of accumulations and chains of precipitates along the grain boundaries and in some volumes of the lath structure (ZrO₂).

The uneven phase precipitates particles distribution leads to an increase in dislocation density in local microvolumes near the precipitates themselves and along grain boundaries, which contributes to an increase in strength and a decrease in the toughness level of the weld metal (welds 0 and Ti). A decrease in the bainitic transformation start temperature contributes to the uneven redistribution of crystal lattice defects at different densities. As a result, there is an increase in dislocation density from $\rho \sim (4 \dots 6) 10^{10} \text{cm}^{-2}$ (in the laths volume) to $\rho \sim (2 \dots 3) 10^{11} \text{cm}^{-2}$ in local microvolumes (near phase precipitates) and the formation of defor-

mation localization zones, which contributes to an uneven level of mechanical properties and a decrease in the metal crack resistance (Table 3).

Calculation methods for assessing internal stresses in local structural zones based on experimental data of fine structure analysis [18] made it possible to establish that the maximum local internal stresses are concentrated along the boundaries of the upper bainite (Ti, SiC and TiC seams) and are initiation potential sources of submicrocracks propagation, t. e. processes cracking (the values of these quantities are 2 ... 3 times higher than in the lower bainite structures).

Fig. 4. The results of the internal stresses calculated assessment in local structural zones

The local stresses increased level is upper bainite structure characteristic and makes it possible to provide a certain level of the weld metal strength, while the presence of lower bainite in the structure makes it possible to increase the toughness level. Ensuring the required set of weld metal mechanical properties when welding low-alloy high-strength steels in each case is

achieved by establishing a certain balance between these two morphological ferrite forms. The results shown in Figs. 4 and 5 show that the dispersed inoculants introduction into the weld pool makes it possible to increase the weld metal toughness while maintaining a sufficiently high strength level.

Fig. 5 Bainitic transformation start temperature influence on the weld metals mechanical properties

Conclusions

The dispersed inoculants introduction into the weld pool is accompanied by a change in the bainitic transformation start temperature (B_s) in the weld metal. The structure of the investigated weld metals is differs in the composition and the carbide phase distribution. Increasing in B_s leads to increases alloyed carbides phase precipitates proportion both in the bainite grains body and along their boundaries. In addition, compounds inoculated nanosized particles into the weld pool are fixed at the grain boundaries.

It is shown that a sharp increase in hardening are result of upper bainite with a high density of dislocations ($\rho \sim (2 \dots 3) \cdot 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) along the lath structure boundaries. The most phase precipitates saturating leads to an increase in dislocation and dispersion hardening. Changes in the phase precipitates morphology, caused by the dispersed inoculants introduction into the weld pool, make it possible to reduce the inhomogeneity of dislocation density distribution at grain boundaries, promote a fine-grained fragmented substructure formation with more uniform bainite distribution. As a result, there is a decrease in the dislocation density in the laths volume and in local microvolumes near the phase precipitates, which provides an increase in the weld metal resistance against brittle fracture.

It is shown that the use of dispersoid inoculants in welding high-strength low-alloy steels promotes a fine-grained structure formation in weld metal, consisting mainly of upper and lower bainite, with a uniform a phase precipitates particles distribution and the absence of noticeable gradients in the dislocation distribution density. The such phase structural components formation is promising from the optimizing the strength, ductility and toughness of the weld metal.

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